

AN OPEN PATH FROM THE ANTENNA TO SCIENTIFIC-GRADE GNSS PRODUCTS

Carles Fernández-Prades¹, Javier Arribas¹, Marc Majoral¹, Jordi Vilà-Valls¹, Alberto García-Rigo², and Manuel Hernández-Pajares²

¹*Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA), Castelldefels, Spain*

²*Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Barcelona, Spain*

ABSTRACT

The availability of hardware and software whose design and source code are published under open licenses (that allow the practical inspection and modification of the full GNSS receiver's chain) opens new opportunities and challenges for science. While raw GNSS signals samples storage and processing is now possible with open tools (making it possible to replay experiments over signals captured in the past and to test new approaches in fair comparison conditions), experimental reproducibility still poses some challenges that can be mitigated with good practices in the reporting of scientific experiments in which open GNSS receivers are involved. This paper discusses reproducibility in the described context, suggesting possible solutions and practical examples.

Key words: software-defined radio, signal processing, Global Navigation Satellite Systems, reproducibility.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper discusses software-defined GNSS receiver technology as a tool for scientific purposes, with potential positive implications in the economical growths of different regions (like Southern Europe and China, India and Brazil). Topics such as space weather, GNSS reflectometry, precise timing or precise farming often require non-standard features from the GNSS receivers, as well as a complete description of the signal processing applied from the antenna up to the computation of the desired GNSS product (which could be observables, position, timing, or any other measure from intermediate stages). However, researchers need to deal with an increasing complexity and integration level of GNSS integrated circuits (ICs), resulting in the practical impossibility of having an exact model on how the desired measurements were obtained and a blocked access to modify or even inspect any internal aspect of the receiver. If the required measurement is already provided by an existing manufactured receiver, one can resort to statistical characterization and fit models upon it. If the required measurement or process is not implemented by an existing

IC, researchers face the complex and costly task of building a brand new receiver from scratch, which is often far from their field of knowledge or subject of interest.

Software-defined receivers have a longstanding recognition to be the technology of choice when a researcher faces the need of obtaining GNSS products that are not already delivered by commercially available IC-based receivers. This popularity is driven by the notion that replacing hardwired, closed circuits by lines of source code provides researchers with unlimited capability to change and customize any aspect of the receiver, from the overall architecture to the algorithmics and the fine tuning, and thus they are empowered to do anything they need. Unfortunately, this is an extremely naive vision.

Commercial software-defined GNSS receivers use to contain proprietary code, distributed in binary form and with no possible inspection by a researcher external to the company that developed the software. Those programs use to provide an extensive application programming interface (API) that allows for fine adjustment of receiver parameters, and some of them even permit user-defined algorithms for certain processing functions. However, they still can be considered black boxes in which we can inject some stimuli (that is, the complete receiver configuration and the stream of signal samples to be processed) and obtain some outputs (the GNSS products, such as observables and navigation data and possibly other pre-defined performance indicators), but only with partial information about the actual signal processing taking place and limited access for modification.

This problem is overcome by software-defined GNSS receivers released under Free and Open Source Software (FOSS) licenses, which allow researchers to share the actual source code and provide users with an explicit permission to modify it. Users can download the source code, make modifications at their wish, create an executable upon it in their own machine, and run any kind of experiment.

While FOSS licenses allow for the possibility of the full inspection of every single step in the signal processing chain, from the sample stream ingestion in the computer platform up to the obtention of the desired GNSS signal products, and its arbitrary modification, sharing the code

still does not ensure some basic requirements for any scientific research: *reproducible* experiments and the practical possibility of modifying existing code. These features require *i*) a careful design of the software architecture, allowing for arbitrary expansion, and where testability has been taken into account from the scratch; *ii*) the possibility to interact with many different radio-frequency front-ends, sample formats, data collection topologies and processing platforms; *iii*) comprehensive and updated documentation; public fora to contact other users and developers, or to get professional assistance; and *iv*) possibility to extract measurements in standard formats in order to chain the receiver outputs to other existing tools. This paper discusses aspects of software-defined GNSS receivers required for scientific experimentation, based on the experience and lessons learned by the authors (as developers and scientific users of GNSS-SDR [GNS17], an open source, software-defined GNSS receiver), building on the work presented in [FAC16] and exposed for public discussion at [Des17], and expanding it to more specifically scientific-related needs.

2. REPRODUCIBILITY

An experiment involving a software-defined GNSS receiver is an experiment that occurs in a computer system. It is well known that today’s computational environments are complex, and accounting for all the possible effects of changes within and across systems is a challenging task [VKV09, Pen11, Irv16]. In computer systems research, an experiment is defined by the workload, the specific system where the workload runs, and the results from a particular execution. A key aspect in order to obtain meaningful conclusions from the experiments is *reproducibility*, which refers to the ability of an entire experiment or study to be reproduced, either by the researcher or by someone else working independently. It is one of the main principles of the scientific method and relies on *ceteris paribus* (other things being equal). Publication of scientific theories, including experimental and observational data on which they are based, permits others to scrutinize them, to replicate experiments, identify errors, to support, reject or refine theories and to reuse data for further understanding and knowledge. Facilitating sustained and rigorous analysis of evidence and theory is the most rigorous form of peer review, and contributes to science’s powerful capacity for self-correction [TRS12].

As described in [JMM⁺15], this feature can be classified into *workload reproducibility* (which requires access to the original code and the particular workload that was used to obtain the original experimental results); *system reproducibility* (which requires access to hardware and software resources that resemble the original dependencies, including the set of hardware devices involved in the experiment such as the antenna, the radio frequency front-end, specific CPU models, possible computing off-loading devices and network elements, system configuration, as well as the entire software stack, from the firmware/kernel version up to the libraries used by the ex-

periment) and *results reproducibility* (the degree to which the results of the re-execution of an experiment are valid with respect to the original). It follows a discussion of those aspects from the perspective of experiments in which software-defined GNSS receivers are involved.

2.1. Workload Reproducibility

In the context of this paper, workload reproducibility refers to the availability of the source code implementing the GNSS receiver, and either a real-time stream of incoming samples delivered by a radio frequency front-end, or those samples stored in files with a given format and data topology.

Obtaining the exact version in which the original experiment was performed is not always straightforward, since source code is inherently dynamic. Bug fixes, improvement and the addition of new features to the code base are frequent, so it is important to have unique identifiers for each source code snapshot. This is solved by version control systems such as Git [Cha09, BDW16], which has become a standard *de facto* for code sharing due to its support for distributed and non-linear workflows, and its associated hosting services such as GitHub or BitBucket. Git assigns a unique identifier to every repository change (called “commits”) obtained by a cryptographic SHA-1 hash function of the whole source tree of the commit (not just the changes), the parent commit SHA-1 hash function, the author and committer information (date, name and email), and the commit message. Hence, a researcher can refer to a particular code snapshot and others can retrieve an exact copy of it. This includes the complete description of the receiver’s configuration used in the experiment. For significant code releases, another good practice is to assign a digital object identifier (DOI) to them for easier citation.

When applied to software engineering, reproducibility has other additional implications such as in security (*i.e.*, gaining confidence that a distributed binary code is indeed coming from a given verified source code). A build is reproducible if given the same source code, build environment and build instructions, any party can recreate bit-by-bit identical copies of all specified artifacts. In the open source community there are well-established good practices (see [Rep17]) which create a verifiable path from human readable source code to the binary code used by computers. This includes [Bob15]: *i*) the build system needs to be made entirely deterministic: transforming a given source must always create the same result; *ii*) the set of tools used to perform the build and more generally the build environment should either be recorded or pre-defined; and *iii*) users should be given a way to recreate a close enough build environment, perform the build process, and verify that the output matches the original build.

The other component of the workload is the stream of sampled GNSS signals feeding the software receiver. If

Table 1. Fundamental data collection topologies, as defined by the ION GNSS SDR Standard Working Group

Data Topology
Single band, single-stream, single file.
Multi-band, single-stream, single file.
Multi-stream, single file.
Multi-sensor, single file.
Temporal splitting of files.
Spatial splitting of files.
Spatial-temporal splitting.

the original experiment reported results obtained in real-time with live GNSS signals, using a radio frequency front-end to feed the software receiver input, the exact conditions of the experiment are impossible to reproduce. This can be solved by storing the sample stream in files that can then be read and processed by the software receiver. Storing the samples delivered by the radio frequency front-end ensures that the experiment will be reproducible by others in the future. Although it still poses some technical challenges, such as the availability of high-bandwidth storage systems, storage capacity and means of sharing such large amount of data (as a example: storing L1 signals with a bandwidth of 20 MHz and with 16 bits per sample during 6 months takes more than 1 petabyte of data), it is becoming a trending practice in scientific experiments with software-defined GNSS receivers. In addition to allow reproducibility, sample storage would also allow in the future for corroboration or rebuttal of the obtained conclusions by other yet-to-be-invented methods.

There is still no well-established standard for GNSS signals sample storage. A relevant effort is being done by the ION GNSS SDR Standard Working Group, which defines some fundamental data collection topologies for raw GNSS, and possibly other sensors, data stored digitally (reproduced in Table 1), sample resolution (including 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32 or 64 bits per sample), encoding (sign, sign-magnitude, signed integer, offset binary or floating point), sampling frequency, possible intermediate frequency and inverted spectrum indicator. The mentioned Working Group is proposing a metadata standard that defines parameters and a formal XML schema to express the contents of GNSS sampled data files [ION17], allowing researchers to share the file(s) containing the data and a metadata file containing the format description of such data.

Finally, it is recommended to include a description of the location and date in which the GNSS signals were captured, including the type of receiver according to its antenna dynamics (see Table 2 for a possible classification), and description of surroundings as needed (nearby buildings and other scatterers, possible presence of interference sources, and any other information considered relevant for the interpretation of the results). A 360-degree picture taken from the antenna location for static receivers, or a 360-degree, time-tagged video for moving platforms could be informative in certain scenarios.

Table 2. Types of receivers according to its antenna dynamics, as defined in RINEX (Receiver Independent Exchange Format) version 3.02

Receiver Type	Description
Geodetic	Earth-fixed high-precision monument.
Non Geodetic	Earth-fixed low-precision monument.
Non Physical	Generated from network processing.
Space borne	Orbiting space vehicle.
Air borne	Aircraft, balloon, etc.
Water Craft	Mobile water craft.
Ground Craft	Mobile terrestrial vehicle.
Fixed Buoy	“Fixed” on water surface.
Floating Buoy	Floating on water surface.
Floating Ice	Floating ice sheet, etc.
Glacier	“Fixed” on a glacier.
Ballistic	Rockets, shells, etc.
Animal	Animal carrying a receiver.
Human	Human being.

2.2. System Reproducibility

System reproducibility requires the full description of the hardware and software resources that resemble the original experimental setup, including the set of hardware devices involved in the experiment such as the antenna, the radio frequency front-end, specific CPU models, possible computing off-loading devices (such as GPUs or FPGAs) and network elements, system configuration, as well as the entire software stack from the firmware/kernel up to the libraries used by the experiment.

2.2.1. Hardware description

The antenna should be described by its manufacturer, identification number and type. In case of multiple antennas, its geometrical arrangement must be provided. Other relevant data is the average antenna phase center relative to the antenna reference point (ARP) for each specific frequency band and satellite system, the orientation of the antenna zero-direction as well as the direction of its vertical axis (bore-sight), if mounted tilted on a fixed station, or XYZ vector in a body-fixed system, in case of mounted on a moving platform (all units in meters). If the antenna is physically apart from the front-end the cable category and length, as well as the connectors type, should be reported.

In case of using a signal generator instead of live GNSS signals, its brand and model (or version if it is a software-defined generator), as well as the complete set of configuration parameters should be included in the experiment description.

Regarding the description of the radio-frequency front-end originally used to capture the GNSS sampled signals used in the experiment, it should include as many details as possible about its electrical features. There are many commercial off-the-shelf solutions in the mar-

ket that act as radio frequency front-ends for GNSS signals. Some of them even share the schematics, bill of materials, printed circuit board layout data, and everything that is necessary for its manufacture, provided the access to the required fabrication tools, materials and components. Notable examples are the HackRF board by Great Scott Gadgets, which design is freely available in a git repository, and the BladeRF board by Nuand, which design is also freely available. Such physical artifacts are usually referred to as open-source hardware, and belong to a broader paradigm known as Open Design [Avi11, Ope17], defined as design artifact projects whose source documentation is made publicly available so that anyone can study, modify, distribute, make, prototype and sell artifacts based on those designs. The artifact's source, the design documentation from which it is made, is available in the preferred format for making modifications to it. Ideally (but not exclusively necessary), Open Design uses readily-available components and materials, standard processes, open infrastructure, unrestricted content, and open-source design tools to maximize the ability of individuals to make and use reproducible hardware.

If custom modifications were made to a commercially available front-end (for instance, replacing and/or disciplining the shipped local oscillator with a more stable clock), those modifications should be also clearly described.

However, having the schematics of a printed circuit board for a RF front-end, or the VHDL model of a FPGA firmware, still does not ensure reproducibility due to *place and route*, a stage in the design of printed circuit boards, integrated circuits, and FPGAs. The first step, placement, involves deciding where to place all electronic components, circuitry, and logic elements in a generally limited amount of space. It assigns logic blocks to specific chip/board locations, trying to minimize the routing distance and therefore allowing successful routing. The second step, routing, decides the exact design of all the wires needed to connect the placed components, optimizing the delay of critical signals. Those operations are usually performed by electronic design automation (EDA) tools, which implement algorithms such as simulated annealing or similar for placing, and pathfinder for routing [Fei14]. Those approaches are heuristic, randomly initialized, and their results are non-deterministic. This means that every run of the route and place process could end up with a different distribution of components in the FPGA or printed circuit board. Although the results are guaranteed to meet the tolerance ranges defined by the designer, this feature poses an extra challenge to reproducibility for printed circuit boards defined by their schematic and for FPGA firmwares defined by their VHDL model.

Even when code and data are shared, it remains difficult to reproduce results due to differing underlying computing platform that is executing the software receiver: processor architecture, memory, storage and communication speed within the different components may vary in different machines. In an experiment report, it is recom-

mended to annotate the processor architecture (*e.g.*, i386, x86_64/amd64, armhf or arm64), manufacturer and type; the available RAM memory and, when relevant, the storage capacity. If computing off-loading devices were used (such as FPGAs or GPUs), its vendor and model should be also specified.

2.2.2. Software stack description

Most software applications, as is the case of software-defined GNSS receivers, do not rely exclusively on their source code. They require features provided by the underlying operating system (for example, Windows, macOS or Linux) as well as a set of supporting libraries (either required or optional) that are called from the main program. This poses a problem to reproducibility, since a researcher replicating the original experiment should install exactly the same version of the operating system, apply the same software upgrades, use the same versions for all the dependency libraries, and the same version of the kernel and other required firmware (that is, the whole software stack that is supporting the main program) than in the original setup. Even if the complete list of dependencies and versions were reported, reproducing the same combination in another machine is not straightforward. While software package managing tools use to ease the upgrading of software components to get the most recent release, they in general do not allow rewinding the system to old versions. In addition, different operating systems (and versions thereof) may require different installation and configuration steps.

A possible solution for researchers is to share not only the source code of the main program and the input data but the whole software stack, including the entire operating system and all software, scripts, code and data necessary to execute the experiment [PF16]. This approach is known as software virtualization, which consists of an encapsulation of the whole software stack that can be executed on practically any desktop, laptop or server, irrespectively of the main ("host") operating system installed on the computer that is actually executing it.

A virtualized software application is a program that can be executed regardless the underlying computer platform (*i.e.*, processor architecture, operating system and installed library versions) that is executing it. This can be achieved by packaging the application and all its software requirements (the operating system and all the application-required supporting libraries and programs) in a single, self-contained and isolated software entity, that can be then run on any platform. Hence, for instance, using virtualization tools a complete Windows system can be run on a Linux machine, or on another version of Windows. An instance of a software-defined GNSS receiver executed in a virtual environment can then be called a *virtualized GNSS receiver* [FPA⁺17]. This is a very convenient strategy for sharing the full software stack as well as data and all the scripts required to reproduce the plots from the original paper. There are two

main approaches to software virtualization: virtual machines and software containers.

A virtual machine (VM) is a software-based environment designed to simulate a hardware-based environment, for the sake of the applications it will host. A VM emulates a computer architecture and provides the functionality of a physical computer. Within each virtual machine runs a full operating system, so conventional software applications expecting to be managed by an operating system and executed by a set of processor cores (*e.g.*, a software-defined GNSS receiver) can run within a VM without any required change. In addition, the researcher has full control over the virtual (“guest”) operating system, and thus can install software, examine scripts and code, and modify configuration settings as necessary.

Recently, however, software containers are replacing VMs as the preferred supporting software stack system for virtualized software applications because of the faster and more lightweight nature of the former. An application running in a container can be more efficient in making use of the underlying hardware than when it is executed on a VM (since it operates directly with the real processing units instead of against an emulated layer, avoiding its overhead [FFRR15]), and many more containers than VMs can be put onto a single server, thus optimizing the investment in compute resources. The concept of containerization was originally developed as a mechanism to segregate namespaces in a Linux operating system for security purposes, isolating process groups (a process and possible descendant processes) from the outside world. The first approach consisted of producing partitions (sometimes called “jails”) within which applications of questionable security or authenticity could be executed without risk to the kernel. The kernel was still responsible for execution, though a layer of abstraction was inserted between the kernel and the workload. Once the environment within these partitions was minimized for efficiency’s sake, the concept expanded to make the contents of those partitions portable. Hence, this technology can be seen as an advanced implementation of the standard chroot mechanism in UNIX-like systems. The first container system was Linux Containers (LXC), followed by a container hypervisor (LXD), and then by other projects such as Docker or Ubuntu Snaps. These latter systems provide native environments with no hypervisor but a daemon that supplements the host kernel and that maintains the compartmentalization between containers, while connecting the kernel to their workloads. Other solutions, such as Virtuozzo’s, allow the creation of encrypted containers for security purposes.

In [BG17], authors proposed a continuous analysis process combining Docker containers with continuous integration, a popular software development technique consisting of the verification of each new commit to the source code by an automated build, to automatically re-run computational analysis whenever relevant changes are made to the source code. This allows results to be reproduced quickly, accurately and without needing to con-

tact the original authors. It also provides an audit trail for analyses that use data with sharing restrictions.

2.3. Results Reproducibility

In computer science, a deterministic algorithm is an algorithm which, given a particular input, will always produce the same output, with the underlying machine always passing through the same sequence of states. If the software-defined receiver is implemented as a single-threaded program (for instance, as a MATLAB script with no parallelization), where the instructions are always called in the same order, without using external states other than the input, operates in a way that is no timing-sensitive and without unexpected hardware errors, the program can be deterministic, which offers many benefits for debugging, fault tolerance, and security, in addition to make reproducibility easier.

However, the computational load required by software-defined GNSS receivers, and their inherently parallelizable architecture design (*e.g.*, many channels performing very similar operations over the same input sample stream), drive to concurrent programming in order to exploit the full capacity of the underlying processors and to improve the processing efficiency. Parallelism poses many correctness challenges, from dealing with concurrency errors like data races, atomicity violations, and ordering violations, to coping with the nondeterminism inherent in most parallel systems. In such cases, a thread scheduler can play a key role in achieving efficiency (that is, real-time processing) while avoiding problems related to nondeterministic executions.

Software-defined receivers can be formally represented as flow graph of nodes. Each node represents a signal processing block, whereas links between nodes represents a flow of data. The concept of a flow graph can be viewed as an acyclic directional graph with one or more source blocks (to insert samples into the flow graph), one or more sink blocks (to terminate or export samples from the flow graph), and any signal processing blocks in between. Those flow graph computations can be jointly modeled as a Kahn process [Kah74, KM77]. A Kahn process describes a model of computation where processes are connected by communication channels to form a network. Processes produce data elements or tokens and send them along a communication channel where they are consumed by the waiting destination process. Communication channels are the only method processes may use to exchange information. Kahn requires the execution of a process to be suspended when it attempts to get data from an empty input channel. A process may not, for example, test an input for the presence or absence of data. At any given point, a process can be either enabled or blocked waiting for data on only one of its input channels: it cannot wait for data from more than one channel.

Systems that obey Kahn’s mathematical model are determinate: the history of tokens produced on the communication channels does not depend on the execution order

[Kah74]. With a proper scheduling policy, it is possible to implement software defined radio process networks holding two key properties: *i) non-termination*: understood as an infinite running flow graph process without deadlocks situations, and *ii) strictly bounded*: the number of data elements buffered on the communication channels remains bounded for all possible execution orders. An analysis of such process networks scheduling was provided in [Par95].

An open source example of a runtime scheduler fulfilling the requirements described in [Par95] is found in GNU Radio, a software framework for programming software-radio applications. A detailed description of such scheduler implementation (memory management, requirement computations, and other related algorithms and parameters) can be found in [Ron13]. Under this scheme, software-defined signal processing blocks read the available samples in their input memory buffer(s), process them as fast as they can, and place the result in the corresponding output memory buffer(s), each of them being executed in its own, independent thread. This strategy results in a software receiver that always attempts to process signal at the maximum processing capacity, since each block in the flow graph runs as fast as the processor, data flow and buffer space allows, regardless of its input data rate, while allowing for a determinate system. However, even using a deterministic scheduler, it still does not ensure the exact replication of results from two different runs. Many factors can affect the obtained numerical results, most notably *i) the workload and resources of the machine running the experiment; ii) the receiver's a priori knowledge of time, ephemeris, almanac and rough position; iii) the availability to data external to the receiver (as is the case of DGNSS and A-GNSS solutions, or the combination with other sensors); and iv) the use of other programming practices that violate Kahn's model and result in a nondeterminate system (e.g., use of shared variables to circumvent the communication channels).*

Another factor that has an impact on GNSS-related experiments' results is satellites' geometry. In order to make the measurement as independent as possible of this effect, measurements should be spread in an interval of 8 hours (see [Hay06]).

Hence, for the all the reasons described along this paper, getting exactly the same numerical results in two different experiments can be extremely difficult, if not impossible, to achieve. In such cases, it make sense to define equivalence criteria for different result sets. A possible tool for the assessment of equivalence between the outputs of different experiments are equivalence tests, a variation of hypothesis tests used to draw statistical inferences from observed data. In equivalence tests, the null hypothesis is defined as an effect large enough to be deemed interesting, specified by an equivalence bound. The alternative hypothesis is any effect that is less extreme than said equivalence bound. The observed data is statistically compared against the equivalence bounds. Examples are the two sample t-test and the two one-sided t-test (TOST) [Wel10].

3. CASE STUDY: GNSS-SDR

Reproducibility requirements have an impact in how a software-defined GNSS receiver is designed, implemented, documented and shared. While strictly speaking reproducibility is only possible with exactly the same setup than in the original experiment, in practice it is desirable to allow the reproduction in the widest range of systems as possible, in order to make possible such replication to researchers with access to other kind of equipment (for instance, a computer with different features, operating system or library versions). This section describes some of the design choices and features related to reproducibility taken in GNSS-SDR, an open source project that implements a GNSS software-defined receiver. With no claim of optimality, this is aimed to provide a working example for the topics discussed in Section 2.

- The source code is released under the GNU General Public License version 3. Some specific files are released under other compatible licenses. All those licenses provide users with the freedom to run the program as their wish, for any purpose; the freedom to study how the program works, and to make modifications at their wish; and the freedom to redistribute copies (and the modified versions) to others.
- GNSS-SDR was accepted as a software package by the Debian Project, and it is available in their most recent releases. This secures software availability in a wide list of other popular GNU/Linux distributions (e.g., Ubuntu) and ensures correctness in terms of licensing and the availability of software dependencies in a large list of processor architectures. A Macports package is also available for macOS.
- The source code is kept under a version control system by Git, a free and open source tool that automates the process of keeping an annotated history of the project, allowing reversion of code changes, easy branching and merging, sharing and change tracking, and the coordination of work on those files among multiple people in a distributed fashion.
- GNSS-SDR's reference Git repository, also referred to as "upstream", is hosted online by GitHub (see <https://github.com/gnss-sdr/gnss-sdr>), a web-based Git repository hosting service which offers all of the distributed revision control and source code management functionality of Git as well as adding its own features, such as review changes, comment on lines of code, report issues, and plan the evolution of the project with discussion tools, all in a rich web-based graphical interface. In this repository there are two development branches with infinite lifetime:
 - `master` is the main, most stable branch that contains the latest software release plus some occasional, portability-related bug fixes, and
 - `next` is where all the code development is happening, containing the most updated code

that will eventually form part of the next stable release.

In addition, the repository offers source code releases packet in a single file and its digital signature, to make easier their distribution and future reference.

- A DOI is issued by Zenodo.org for each software release (e.g., [FAE17]).
- In order to address reproducibility of the source code building rules (compiler flags, linking, etc.), GNSS-SDR uses CMake as its building system generator. CMake is used to control the software compilation process using platform and compiler independent configuration files, from which it generates native *makefiles* and *workspaces* that can be used in a wide range of compiler environments. Popular open source build automation tools, such as Make and Ninja, can be used to automatically build the required executable programs and libraries from the source code with the aid of the building files generated by CMake. Using popular, widely available cross-platform tools helps to ensure portability among different systems and processor architectures.
- The source code can be compiled with the two most popular open source compilers, GCC and LLVM/Clang. In general, it is desirable to be able to build the source code with different compilers, since it improves the overall quality of code by providing different checks and alerts.
- GNSS-SDR's source code honors the C++11 and C++14 standards [C++14], thus ensuring the validity of the source code in a wide range of processing platforms and compilers for a long time span (in computer science's time scale).
- A "Dockerfile" example for the generation of GNSS-SDR Docker containers is available at <https://github.com/carlesfernandez/docker-gnssdr>. Docker is an open source tool designed to make it easier to create, deploy, and run applications by using software containers. Docker containers wrap a piece of software in a complete filesystem that contains everything needed to run: code, runtime, system tools and system libraries, and ship it all out as one package. This guarantees that the software will always run the same, regardless of any customized settings that the executing machine might have that could differ from the machine used for writing and testing the code.
- Project website at <http://gnss-sdr.org>, containing building instructions, tutorials, and the documentation about the receiver's configuration. The website source content is available as a Git repository at <https://github.com/gnss-sdr/geniuss-place>.
- GNSS signal products delivered in standard output formats such as RINEX files (navigation and ob-

servables) in versions 2.11 and 3.02, and RTCM v3.2 messages, with configurable rates.

- Full receiver configuration in a single text file, allowing easy exchange and reference of receiver's full configuration.
- Modular design and runtime scheduler inherited from GNU Radio (see <https://www.gnuradio.org>), a well-established open source software framework for software-defined radio applications.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper discussed the reproducibility of scientific experiments in which a software-defined GNSS receiver plays a role. While reproducibility is largely recognized as an essential feature of the scientific method, it is usual to find scientific papers that fail to provide enough information for the replication of the original experiment by other researchers. Those aspects were analyzed in terms of workload, system and results reproducibility, providing recommendations for reporting experiments in a way that can be reproduced by others. Practical examples of features related to reproducibility in a currently available open source software-defined GNSS receiver were also provided.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been developed in the frame of AUDITOR. This project has received funding from the European GNSS Agency under the European Unions Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 687367. The work was also partially supported by the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness through Project ADVENTURE (TEC2015-69868-C2-2-R).

REFERENCES

- [Avi11] M. Avital. The generative bedrock of open design. In B. van Abel, L. Evers, R. Klaassen, and P. Troxler, editors, *Open design now: why design cannot remain exclusive*, pages 48–58. BIS Publishers, Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 2011.
- [BDW16] J. D. Blischak, E. R. Davenport, and G. Wilson. A quick introduction to version control with Git and Github. *PLoS Computational Biology*, 12(1):1–18, Jan. 2016. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pcbi.1004668.
- [BG17] B. K. Beaulieu-Jones and C. S. Greene. Reproducibility of computational workflows is automated using continuous analysis. *Nature Biotechnology*, 35(4):342–346, Apr. 2017. DOI: 10.1038/nbt.3780.

- [Bob15] J. Bobbio. How to make your software build reproducibly. In *Chaos Communication Camp*, Mildenberg, Germany, 2015.
- [C++14] *Standard ISO/IEC 14882:2014(E) Information technology – Programming languages – C++*. Geneva, Switzerland, Dec. 2014.
- [Cha09] S. Chacon. *Git Pro*. Apress, New York, NY, 2009. Available online at <https://git-scm.com/book/en/v2>.
- [Des17] *GNSS-SDR Website: 16 Design Forces for software-defined GNSS receivers*, 2017. Website: <http://gnss-sdr.org/design-forces/>. Accessed: November 8, 2017.
- [FAC16] C. Fernández-Prades, J. Arribas, and P. Closas. Assessment of software-defined GNSS receivers. In *Proc. of 8th edition of NAVITEC*, pages 1–9, ESA/ESTEC, Noordwijk, The Netherlands, Dec. 2016. DOI: 10.1109/NAVITEC.2016.7931740.
- [FAE17] C. Fernández-Prades, J. Arribas, and L. Esteve. *GNSS-SDR v0.0.9*. Zenodo, Feb. 2017. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.291371.
- [Fei14] T. Feist. *Vivado Design Suite*. Xilinx, Inc., San Jose, CA, June 2014. WP416 (v1.1).
- [FFRR15] W. Felter, A. Ferreira, R. Rajamony, and J. Rubio. An updated performance comparison of virtual machines and Linux containers. In *Proc. of the IEEE Intl. Symp. on Performance Analysis of Systems and Software*, pages 171–172, Philadelphia, PA, Mar. 2015. DOI: 10.1109/ISPASS.2015.7095802.
- [FPA+17] C. Fernández-Prades, C. Pomar, J. Arribas, J.M. Fàbrega, J. Vilà-Valls, M. Svaluto Moreolo, R. Casellas, R. Martínez, M. Navarro, F.J. Vílchez, R. Muñoz, R. Vilalta, L. Nadal, and A. Mayoral. A cloud optical access network for virtualized GNSS receivers. In *Proc. 30th Int. Tech. Meeting Sat. Div. Inst. Navig.*, Portland, OR, Sep. 2017.
- [GNS17] *GNSS-SDR. An Open Source Global Navigation Satellite Systems Software Defined Receiver*, 2017. Website: <http://gnss-sdr.org>. Accessed: November 8, 2017.
- [Hay06] C. Hay. Standardized GPS simulation scenarios for SPS receiver testing. In *Proc. IEEE/ION Position, Location And Navigation Symposium*, pages 1080–1085, San Diego, CA, Apr. 2006.
- [ION17] ION GNSS SDR Standard Working Group. *Global Navigation Satellite Systems Software Defined Radio Sampled Data Metadata Standard Revision 1.0*, Aug 2017. Available from: <https://github.com/IonMetadataWorkingGroup>. Accessed: November 8, 2017.
- [Irv16] D. Irving. A minimum standard for publishing computational results in the weather and climate sciences. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 97(7):1149–1158, Jul. 2016. DOI: 10.1175/BAMS-D-15-00010.1.
- [JMM+15] I. Jimenez, C. Maltzahn, A. Moody, K. Mohror, J. Lofstead, R. Arpaci-Dusseau, and A. Arpaci-Dusseau. The role of container technology in reproducible computer systems research. In *Proc. of the IEEE Intl. Conf. on Cloud Engineering*, pages 379–385, Tempe, AZ, Mar. 2015. DOI: 10.1109/IC2E.2015.75.
- [Kah74] G. Kahn. The semantics of a simple language for parallel programming. In J. L. Rosenfeld, editor, *Information processing*, pages 471–475, Stockholm, Sweden, Aug 1974. North Holland.
- [KM77] G. Kahn and D. B. MacQueen. Coroutines and networks of parallel processes. In B. Gilchrist, editor, *Information processing*, pages 993–998, Amsterdam, NE, 1977. North Holland.
- [Ope17] Open Design Working Group. The Open Design Definition v. 0.5. Available from: <https://github.com/OpenDesign-WorkingGroup>, 2017. Accessed: November 8, 2017.
- [Par95] T. M. Parks. *Bounded Scheduling of Process Networks*. PhD thesis, University of California, Berkeley, CA, Dec. 1995.
- [Pen11] R. D. Peng. Reproducible research in computational science. *Science*, 334(6060):1226–1227, Dec. 2011. DOI: 10.1126/science.1213847.
- [PF16] S. R. Piccolo and M. B. Frampton. Tools and techniques for computational reproducibility. *GigaScience*, 30(5):1–13, Jul. 2016. DOI: 10.1186/s13742-016-0135-4.
- [Rep17] *Reproducible builds*, 2017. Website: <https://reproducible-builds.org>. Accessed: November 8, 2017.
- [Ron13] T. W. Rondeau. *Explaining the GNU Radio Scheduler*, Sep. 2013. Slides published online at <http://www.trondeau.com/blog/2013/9/15/explaining-the-gnu-radio-scheduler.html>. Accessed: November 8, 2017.
- [TRS12] The Royal Society. *Science as an open enterprise*. London, UK, June 2012. Report 02/12. ISBN: 978-0-85403-962-3.
- [VKV09] P. Vandewalle, J. Kovačević, and M. Vetterli. Reproducible research in signal processing. *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, 26(3):37–47, May 2009. DOI: 10.1109/MSP.2009.932122.
- [Wel10] S. Wellek. *Testing Statistical Hypotheses of Equivalence and Noninferiority*. CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, 2nd edition, June 2010.